

USING SIX SIGMA TECHNICAL AND THE DIMENSIONS OF LEAN PRODUCTION TO ACHIEVE DISTINGUISHED BANKING SERVICES

Hanan A. Hasan, Raed Majeed Abd Mohammed, and Prof. Dr. Ali Abbas Kareem AL-Khafaji

Higher Institute of Accounting and Financial Studies, Hanan.hasan@dcec.uobaghdad.edu.iq

Technical Administrative College, Raedmajeed1962@mtu.edu.iq

Higher Institute of Accounting and Financial Studies, Ali.Kareem@qu.edu.iq

Introduction

Developed countries have contributed to the progress and development of the banking sector, as it is an important measure of the development of countries, as the interest in banks has increased in terms of their architectural design, furnishing, internal arrangement, external appearances, providing the best services, as well as applying modern management concepts that lead to improving quality and reducing costs and thus achieving high profits. But what the banking sector in Iraq is witnessing is that its work is accompanied by many failures in the performance methods, which results in the provision of low-quality services and high costs, and in the end result in low profits. This research has come to shed light on this problem, at a time when these banks are seeking to achieve a competitive advantage and leadership in the banking business. All these factors have increased the volume of competition to obtain a market share, so the economic units have sought for more openness, innovation, development and creativity for the sake of continuity improvement of quality its services on the one hand and reducing its costs on the other hand, and then staying in the competition market through the emergence of modern administrative systems and methods that had an effective impact on the development of these units. The third was for the practical side, and the research reached several important conclusions and recommendations that were discussed in the fourth and last topic

First: Concept of Six Sigma techniques

This new concept includes measuring, improving and controlling the capabilities of operations in order to build products (goods and services) free from all kinds of defects, and the basic idea is based on measuring the critical customer requirements as goals that the unit seeks to achieve and then performance against these goals during manufacturing instead of achieving those Objectives after making the product (Maguire, 1999:32) On the other hand, when implementing the Six Sigma technique, it works to integrate a wide range of tools and methods through the stages of performance improvement and then improving profits as a final goal, so the units sought to apply this technique for the purpose of reaching A high degree of quality in which losses and defects are reduced in a way that leads to meeting the customer's needs. He deals with this technique from several angles, the most important of which are: - (Ismail, 2006: 18)

1. A statistical measure of performance.
2. A technique aimed at improving operations.
3. Administrative system

The following is an explanation of each of these angles:

- 1- A statistical measure of performance:

It is a statistical method used to indicate the standard deviation in the production or service

process, and to measure the extent to which the values are dispersed from their arithmetic mean. (Al-Nuaimi, 2007: 5) In the field of quality, it indicates that the units that provide services or goods that are free from defects will be at the top of the competition over similar units, and that there will be only (3.4) defects for every million opportunities or almost perfection. (Al-Zahrani, 2010: 21), and for the purpose of determining the level of deviation in any unit, it is required to follow a set of related measures that are used to determine the chances of defects appearing per million opportunities in services and production processes, and these measures include: (Slack & Johnston, 2004: 625)

First scale: percentage of defects = (number of defects / quantity of units produced) x 100%

The second scale: the percentage of accuracy in operations = 1- the percentage of defects

The third metric: Defects per million opportunities = Defects per opportunity x 1,000,000

Table 1: Six Sigma levels and their corresponding defects and outcomes

Six Sigma level	Defects per million	chances Yield %
the first	691,500	30,% pump
the couple	308500	knock,15%
triple	66800	93.32%
Quadrilateral	6200	p,bit%
pentagram	230	y,% true
hexagram	.43	p.99966%

Table (2) represents the numbers per million chances against the standard deviation, i.e. the degree of sex sigma, the errors committed, and the amount of the return ratio for each error, as it is clear from the table that the economic units in which defects or errors occur in the operations of the units produced by an amount of (691,500) errors, they will be considered among the units Which operates at the level of the first Six Sigma, thus achieving a return that does not exceed (30.85%), and as for the economic units that obtain the number of defects between (308500-691500) defects in the operations of their production units, then they will be working at the level of the bilateral Six Sigma with a return rate not exceeding (69.15%) and so on with the rest of the other Six Sigma levels.

Table 2: The Six Steps Applied in Six Sigma Technology for the Industrial and Service Sectors

(Source: (Park, 2003)

Industrial sector	service sector
Determining the physical and technical requirements of the customer.	Determine your business (the service you provide).
Determine critical product characteristics for each order.	Determine who the customer is.
Identification of each characteristic for the purpose of controlling each part or process or both.	Determine what you need for your duties and who are your suppliers
Define the process of difference (change) for each characteristic.	Process map.
Define the process of difference (change) for each characteristic.	Proving the errors of these operations and excluding delays.

If the process performance is less than six, the materials, product and processes will be re-designed as required.

Setting metrics for quality, cycle time, and improvement of objectives

Second: Six Sigma technique as a goal to improve operations:

The goal of the Six Sigma technology is to help people and processes that aim ambitiously to provide products and services free from defects (Al-Naimi and Sweiss, 2008: 55), and that bringing defects to zero has no room within the work where the Six Sigma technology realizes that there is always room for error even Within the best processes or within the best production (Al-Zahrani, 2010: 21) and to achieve a performance level of 99,99966%, the Six Sigma technology makes the defects in products and services almost non-existent (Bin Said, 2004: 55-56).

Because of the importance of this technology, it has begun to be used in the services sector as well, after it was used only to develop processes and products (Al-Hakim, 2008: 4), and the following table (2) shows the six steps applied in the Six Sigma technology for the industrial and non-industrial sectors.

Third: Administrative system

The Six Sigma technology is an integrated administrative system with a high degree of structure to improve the activities of various operations. It represents an administrative organization that provides departments with the methods and analytical tools necessary to solve problems and reach the highest level of quality (Al-Zahrani, 2010: 21), and it is a system that combines strong leadership and motivation And the involvement of the base as well as its benefits, which are not only material, but workers find that working to gain customer satisfaction, clarity of performance processes, setting correct measurements and developing tools makes their work more effective and giving, both in terms of moral and material terms (Al-Nuaimi and Sweis, 2008: 59). The main steps for developing the departments depend on increasing their conviction that the application of the Six Sigma technique will further improve their financial situation, and these steps are: (Al-Nuaimi, 2007: 10-11).

- A - Focus on customer satisfaction.
- b - Reliance on information and facts.
- C - Operations exist where the verb is.
- D - Initiative management.
- E - Unlimited cooperation.
- F - Orientation towards perfection and tolerance of errors.

Second: The concept of service

The concept of service has broad connotations, as it is included in various economic fields and as a result it was considered of distinct importance by society at its different levels. Accordingly, many definitions of the concept of services were received, including the following: It is a benefit that one person can provide to one party to another party that is not necessarily tangible and does not result in ownership of anything (Kotler, 2007: 456). It is appropriate to mention the most important points of difference between the commodity product and the service product, as shown in Table No. (3), which are the following:

Table 3: Differences between commodity and service producers

commodity product	service product
can be resold	It cannot be resold

Be ready before purchase	Not available before purchase
The product is sold out	Presentation of the product and its fulfillment at the same time
can be stored	service product
It does not require direct communication between the producer and the customer	It requires direct communication between the producer and the customer
Easier to measure quality	Complex quality measurement

The customer faces more difficulty when evaluating the service provided to him compared to tangible, physical goods. This is due to the fact that the actual performance of the service is related to the customer’s interaction with the service provider and the experience of the customer himself. Hence, judging the service as good or not good is different from one customer to another and from a certain time. to another to the same customer (Idris, 2006: 29) and units must correct this judgment by using specific retrieval strategies, that is, when the beneficiary is not satisfied with the service provided to him, the unit can re-provide that beneficiary with the service as well as motivate the service provider to work excellent all the time (Bateson, 1995: 335).

Third: The relationship enacts Six Sigma techniques and improves service quality

The relationship of Six Sigma technology to improving service quality can be explained through the following points: (Slack & Johnston, 2004: 625).

- 1- Quality programs focused in the past on meeting the needs of the customer at any cost, and the units were able to produce high quality products despite the inefficiency of the internal processes in them, and the units paid to achieve quality (quality cost), so the units believed that quality costs a lot of effort and money. and time.
- 2- The Six Sigma technique is a natural extension of quality efforts, so it is an initiative to develop quality, as it works to link between the highest quality and the lowest costs of production. The following figure shows the extension and development of Six Sigma from other quality methods.
- 3- Six Sigma cannot work in isolation from quality, as the quality management of this technology provides the necessary tools to bring about cultural changes and the development of processes within the department.
- 4- The Six Sigma technique is a performance goal that is applied to each element of quality and not to the product as a whole. In other words, quality focuses on the quality of the final product and has a cost. As for Six Sigma, it focuses on operations to achieve product quality at the lowest cost.
- 5- The Six Sigma technology is not about quality for the sake of quality itself, but rather about providing better value to customers, employees and investors.
- 6- For the purpose of determining the level of Six Sigma technology in any unit, it is required to follow a set of related metrics that are used to determine the chances of defects appearing for every million opportunities in products and production processes.

Fourth: Dimensions of Lean banking services

(Gopalakrishnan, 2010: 41), according to the researcher, that agile banking includes five dimensions, which are as shown in Figure 1:

- 1- Customer value.
- 2- Value Stream.
- 3- Value Flow.
- 4- Customer pull.
- 5- Bank Services by Continues improvement

In light of the foregoing, it became clear that there is a similarity between the elements of agile services and their exclusion, through the references of researchers in this field.

1- customer value

A- The concept and definition of customer value The value of business in the twenty-first century is focused on the value of the customer, so giving all he wants of new or developed products that are compatible with his expectations is what achieves customer value. Also, that value is seen as achieving customer needs better than any another one at the lowest cost. (Taher, 2006:79).

There are four concepts of customer value:

1. Value as the lowest price
2. It is whatever the customer desires, the service or the product
3. The quality that the customer receives
4. What the customer gets in return for what he pays. Al-Janabi (2006: 61(
5. It has also been defined as the difference between the total customer value and the total customer cost, and the total customer cost is (which is a set of customer costs, except for those that are achieved in evaluating, obtaining, and using the product) (Taher, (79: 2006.(

2- Value Stream

The value stream is one of the main elements or dimensions on which the agile production and services system is based. The researcher agrees with what he mentioned (Abdullah, 2003:40) that the value stream dimension has many benefits, including:

- 1- Through which waste can be distinguished and its source also diagnosed.
- 2- It helps to form a base for applying slimming in the production and service process.
- 3- It helps to know and understand the operational flow of the production and service process.
- 4- It helps to know and understand the necessary and non-essential activities for the production and service flow processes.

The researcher shares the description of (Beckman & Rosen Field, 2008: 371) that the value stream activities are the activities that are used to improve the flow of processes in production and services and to plan for each step in the processes through which it is possible to identify the necessary as well as unnecessary steps in improving the performance of operations and what It is the added value to the operations and services provided to customers.

1-Continuous improvement (Kaizen)

Continuous improvement is one of the important dimensions in agile production and services, and they represent the main base for adopting agile production and services. They are a basis for the success of organizations. Whatever level the organization has reached, it remains room for continuous improvement because standing at a certain level allows competitors to exceed the level reached by the organization. In order to achieve continuous improvement, it is necessary to

support the senior management, the availability of a long-term vision, the participation of all employees in the organization, in addition to the organization's adoption of the necessary and supportive structures related to management, training, resource distribution, rewards and incentives system. (Obeidat, 2010: 225).

And both (Pearce & Robinson, 2003: 331) and (Goetsch & Davis, 2010: 653) indicated that continuous improvement can be achieved through the application of the 6-Sigma methodology, which aims to improve products and increase customer satisfaction through providing performance Best

2- Attracting the customer (response)

Providing services to customers at the expected speed and confronting crises, problems and customer complaints with quick and sound solutions. The waiting period for the customer to answer his request should be short, and the administration should work on the continuity of providing its services at all times of the day, and that the provision of services to customers by employees without any hesitation or boredom.

3- Value Stream

The flow chart is described as a graphic representation of the process steps, which helps to identify opportunities for improvement through a deep understanding of the reality of the process by revealing the sources of the underlying problems and their relationship to each other. The diagram is shown with easy-to-observe symbols, and the diagram is used to describe an existing process or design a new process (Al-Qazzaz and others, 2009: 85). Among the advantages of the flow diagram are the following: (Al-Shaheen, 2001: 47)

A - Determine the best areas for data collection.

B - Sorting and tracing the origin of the beginning of the problem.

C - Determine the possibility of reducing the distance required by the service path.

D- Determining all the steps of the conversion process that represent potential locations for testing stations.

Fourth: The types of nonsense that the production of agile banking services has eliminated

One of the main objectives that the production of agile services seeks to achieve is the removal of waste, as the production of agile services means the pursuit of leanness in services, and this can only be achieved by eliminating all types of waste. The researcher agrees with the opinions of some researchers (Apel, et.al, 2007: 9) (Krajewsky, et.al, 2010: 297-298) (Heizer & Render, 2011: 654). And (Al-Hasnawi, 2013: 55)

The types of waste in the production of banking services are:

- 1- Waste resulting from the increase in the production of services: which means producing more than what the customer requires, which entails additional costs, especially with regard to services that may not have a market for customers.
- 2- Wastage resulting from the lack of modern technological technologies: This type of waste occurs as a result of the lack of credit cards (electronic cards), which are considered one of the most important modern banking tools and other means of using modern counting methods.
- 3- Waste due to movement: This type of waste occurs as a result of the processes of scientific arrangement of banking offices and divisions from one work site to another, so banks seek

to reduce the travel distances between work sites in order to eliminate this type of waste during the movement of customers.

- 4- Wastage due to waiting time: This type of waste occurs due to the imbalance of banking operations and waiting times between the stages through which the service is provided, and this leads to a waste of time and money.
- 5- Waste during operations: This type of waste occurs as a result of the increase in operations during the completion of work in order to meet the requirements of the customer, which leads to the use of more resources than what is required.
- 6- Waste resulting from employees' misuse of computers and banking machines: which leads to an increase in service costs, as well as the time taken to conduct the inspection process and fix defects in services.
- 7- Wastage due to movement: This type of waste occurs as a result of unnecessary movements and the transition from one process to another by the workers, and this leads to increased stress and time loss, which entails additional costs. Figure (6) shows the seven types of waste

1- Fifth: Characteristics of the Lean Banking Production System

2- The production of agile banking services has many characteristics that distinguish it from other production systems and many researchers have referred to it as follows: It was clarified by (Oliver, et.al, 1994: 55) and by the disposal of the researcher as follows:

- 1- Relying on the philosophy of continuous improvement (Kaizen) in solving problems.
- 2- Working on correcting errors before they appear, by using a few assets, such as a small number of workers, and adopting production by small batches for the purpose of preventing errors from occurring before they occur.
- 3- Organizing the work context through work teams that are formed from highly skilled workers and have a high degree of empowerment to complete their work.
- 3- - 4Commitment of global individuals and their ability to participate in decision-making and prevent the occurrence of problems.
- 4- Working on consolidating good relations with customers according to the contexts and regulatory rules of the banking process.
- 5- Moving to the operation directly through the close link between the customer and the banking divisions.

Presentation and interpretation of the results of the survey

This section is concerned with a statistical presentation to test and analyze the relationships shown by the questionnaire forms by analyzing the opinions and responses of a sample of respondents from the research community represented by bank employees. Five-point Likert scale

Table 5: Five-point Likert scale

Totally agree	I agree	Neutral	I don't agree	I don't totally agree
5	4	3	2	1

First: Measuring the validity and reliability of the questionnaire:

Several tests were conducted on the questionnaire to ensure its validity and reliability:

1- Apparent honesty measurement:

It is the ability of the questionnaire form to measure what it was designed for, as the research tool (the questionnaire form) was presented to a group of experts after its initial design. The researcher presented the form in its initial form to a group of arbitrators in various fields of competence

2- Measurement of stability (self-consistency)

The cronbachs alpha coefficient was used to measure the degree of credibility of bank employees on the questionnaire questions, and the value of alpha ranges between (zero -1) and that the statistically acceptable value of the alpha coefficient (60%) or more in order to have good measurement credibility. This coefficient has been calculated. To collect the questionnaire questions, the alpha value of the responses of the study members to the questions was (87%), which is good because it is greater than the first acceptable limit of the reliability coefficient.

Second: General information

Table 6 and Table 7 summarize the results of compiling the answers received from the research sample, which were collected through the questionnaire form, and the following results showed:

Table 6: Qualification

Academic qualification	Number	Percentage
PhD	5	10 %
Master's	5	10%
Bachelor of Accounting	32	64%
Accounting diploma	8	16%
The total	50	100%

Table No. (6) shows that 64% of the research sample members have a bachelor's degree in accounting (the reason for this is that the directors of the Accounting Division, most of them have a bachelor's degree in accounting), and that 10% have a master's degree as well as a doctorate, and the percentage of those with an accounting diploma is 16% . Through the above results, it can be inferred that there is experience with the selected sample.

The above table shows that the sample members have experience, as 36% of the sample have 6–10 years of service, 20% have more than 20 years of service, and from 16-20 their percentage was 12%, and those with 11 years of service - 15 years, their percentage was 18%, and 14% for those whose service was 5 years or less.

Table 7: Years of service

Years of Service	Number	Percentage
More than 20 years	10	20%
16-20	6	12%
11-15	4	18%
6-10	18	36%
5 years or less	7	14%
Total	50	100%

Table (7) shows the presence of experience in the selected sample, represented by employees at 32%, authorized (A) by 20%, authorized (B) by 14%, bank manager by 10% and division head by 24%.

Third: Analyzing the results of the questionnaire:

1- The first axis: the extent to which agile services can be applied

The information, facts, analyzes and interpretations of this axis focused on evaluating the extent to which agile services can be applied in banks. The researcher adopted the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, variance, and Pearson simple correlation for the purpose of conducting a statistical analysis of the responses of the sample members. The hypothetical mean (3) was also used as a criterion for measuring and evaluating the degree obtained and related to the sample responses, within the verbal assessment of the five questionnaire weights, knowing that the hypothetical mean (3) It is an average of the highest score on the scale, which is (5), and the lowest score in it is (1), meaning that:

Table 8: The position occupied by the research sample

Function	the number	The ratio
bank manager	5	10%
Authorized	10	20%
authorized to	7	14%
Division Head	12	24%
Employee	16	32%
the total	50	100%

After conducting the processing and statistical analysis of the responses of the sample respondents, the arithmetic averages, standard deviations, variance and correlation values for each of the axes of the questionnaire and for the axis as a whole were reached, and this can be clarified through the following table:

Table 9: Section one: agile services

N	Paragraphs	Arithmetic mean	deviation	variance
1	he management of the bank stresses the need to organize everything in all the departments of the bank and in all stages of work	4.45	0.668	0.40
2	The management of the bank is concerned with arranging the workplace and distributing the banking divisions in their designated places	4.34	0.624	0.30
3	The management of the bank is concerned with the cleanliness of the workplace constantly to ensure a valid and healthy working environment for employees	4.31	0.722	0.50
4	The management of the bank conducts preventive maintenance operations as a constant approach	4.30	0.759	0.51
5	The management of the bank adopts a policy of self-discipline as a correct method of performing work	4.17	0.733	0.633

	The arithmetic mean, standard deviation ,and general variance of the worksite organization axis	4.43	0.632	0.4
6	The bank management implements a comprehensive and productive maintenance program in all the bank's departments	3.82	0.795	0.633
7	The management of the bank involves the maintenance teams in training courses to improve their performance and develop their skills	4.27	0.521	0.272
8	The maintenance department owns all the necessary devices and equipment to carry out its duties	3.93	0.912	0.832
9	The management of the bank adopts a policy of conducting maintenance operations in order to maintain machinery and equipment and reduce the rate of holidays and interruptions	4.03	0.895	0.801
10	Social and ethical responsibility is a constant curriculum for workers in the maintenance department	3.36	0.733	0.538
	The arithmetic mean standard deviation ,and general variance of the comprehensive maintenance axis (Tm)	4.01	0.741	0.549
11	The management of the bank seeks to spread the culture of eliminating waste (unnecessary activities) in the banking business	4.41	0.620	0.385
12	The management of the bank encourages and stimulates ideas and suggestions submitted by employees, especially those that contribute to providing good banking services	4.72	0.553	0.202
13	The bank's management works to determine the requirements for continuous improvement, whether material or human	4.51	0.502	0.253
14	The bank has highly skilled and experienced individuals who believe that the process of continuous improvement is everyone's responsibility	4.31	0.645	0.426
15	The management of the bank has absolute belief that	3.96	0.663	0.383
	The arithmetic mean standard deviation , and general variance of the continuous improvement axis	4.35	0.556	0.322
16	The bank's management sets a comprehensive and integrated plan for the process of flowing services	4.44	0.723	0.599

	to the customer and for the stages of the banking work			
17	Bank management identifies essential value-creating activities and distinguishes them from non-essential activities that must be eliminated	4.31	0.711	0.496
18	The bank management believes that unnecessary activities represent waste in the banking business and do not add value to the final product	4.17	0.677	0.563
19	Employees have a complete conception of the service flow process from the bank to the customer that creates value for the customer	3.82	1.043	1.191
20	The management of the bank emphasizes the provision of banking services in order to distinguish waste and to diagnose its source as well	3.93	0.932	0.832
Arithmetic mean , standard deviation, and general variance of the variance of the value stream axis		4.31	0.721	0.589
21	Services are provided to the customer at the expected speed or more	4.01	0.741	0.549
22	Confronting crises, problems and guest complaints are characterized by solutions fast and sound	4.41	0.620	0.385
23	The waiting period for the customer to answer his request is short	4.01	0.741	0.549
24	The waiting period for the customer to answer his request is short	4.41	0.620	0.385
25	The administration works on the continuity of providing its services at all times of the day	4.01	0.741	0.549
26	Services are provided to guests by employees without any hesitation or boredom.	4.31	0.610	0.345
The arithmetic mean standard deviation , and general variance of the response axis		4.06	0.877	0.66
The arithmetic mean standard deviation , and general variance of the first section – agile services		4.2	0.884	0.449

It is clear from Table (9) the following results

1. Five - S Workplace Organization: The result of the first axis reached a general arithmetic mean of (4.43), a general standard deviation of (0.632), and a general variance of (0.4), which indicates the strength of the response of the research sample to the movement of the scale used and a small dispersion in The answers, as for the paragraphs level, the arithmetic mean ranged from (4.45) for the first question (the bank's management stresses the need to organize everything in all the bank's departments and in all stages of work) where the standard deviation and variance were (0.688) (0.40), respectively. While the answers to the fifth paragraph (the bank management

adopts a policy of self-discipline as a correct method for performing work) have achieved their lowest level, as the arithmetic mean (4.17), the standard deviation (0.733), and the variance (0.633).

From the foregoing, it is clear that the answers of the research sample are heading towards agreement and this is confirmed by the arithmetic average for this axis, which ranged between (4.84 - 4.17) and is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic average of (3) with a deviation ranging between (0.759 - 0.624) and with little dispersion. This axis enjoys a high degree of internal consistency, and this can be shown through the following table:

Tables 10: Correlation coefficients for each of the paragraphs of the first section : The first axis – the organization of the work site

Paragraph	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	-	-	-	-
2	0.746	1	-	-	-
3	0.771	0.870	1	-	-
4	0.809	0.902	0.906	1	-
5	0.700	0.955	0.835	0.886	1

2.Total Maintenance

The result of this axis indicates the agreement of the research sample that the bank seeks to pay attention to comprehensive maintenance, and this is confirmed by the general arithmetic mean, which reached (4.01), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3), a general standard deviation of (0.741) and a general variance of (0.549). Which indicate the strength of the response of the research sample to the movement of the scale used and a small dispersion in the answers? From the above, it appears that the answers of the research sample are heading towards agreement and this is confirmed by the arithmetic average for this axis, which ranged between (4.27 -3.82) which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic average of (3). Also, this axis enjoys a high degree of internal consistency, and this can be shown through the following table 11: -

Tables 11: Correlation coefficients for each paragraph of the comprehensive maintenance

Paragraph	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	-	-	-	-
2	0.789	1			
3	0.897	0.847	1	-	
4	0.841	0.802	0.943	0.966	1

Value Stream: The answers of the research sample indicate agreement and complete agreement, and this was confirmed by the general arithmetic mean for this axis (4.06), which is higher than the

3- Continuous improvement

The answers of the research sample were heading towards agreement and complete agreement, and this was confirmed by the general arithmetic mean for this axis, which amounted to (4.35), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic average of (3), as well as the standard deviation and general variance (0.556) (0.322), respectively. As for the paragraphs of the axis, the arithmetic mean ranged between (4.72 - 3.96), which is higher than the hypothetical average, as

well as the standard deviation ranged between (0.733 - 0.502), which confirms the homogeneity of the answers of the sample members .. Also, this axis enjoys a high degree of internal consistency and this can be shown via the following table 12:

Table 12: Correlation coefficients for each of the continuous improvement clauses

Paragraph	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	-	-	-	-
2	0.664	1	-	-	-
3	0.872	0.639	1	-	-
4	0.885	0.652	0.781	1	-
5	0.674	0.718	0.619	0.718	1

4- Value stream: The answers of the research sample indicate complete agreement and agreement, and this was confirmed by the general arithmetic mean for this axis (4.06), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic average of (3), as well as the standard deviation and general variance (0.877) (0.66), respectively, which It indicates the strength of the research sample's response to the movement of the scale used and a small dispersion in the answers. Also, this axis enjoys a high degree of internal consistency, and this can be shown through the following table: -4: -

Tables 13: Correlation coefficients for each of the value stream axis paragraphs

Paragraph	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	-	-	-	-
2	0.830	1	-	-	-
3	0.766	0.888	1	-	-
4	0.919	0.888	0.889	1	-
5	0.835	0.848	0.884	0.934	1

5- Response: It is clear through the results of the axis related to the extent of the possibility of response that there is complete agreement and agreement by the research sample, through the general arithmetic mean of the axis, which is (4.06), which is higher than the hypothetical mean, and the results also indicate the presence of a standard deviation of (0.877), which indicates On the strength of the response of the sample members, there is a small dispersion in the answers. Also, this axis enjoys a high degree of internal consistency, and this can be shown through the following table

Tables 14: Correlation coefficients for each of the paragraphs of the response axis

Paragraph	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1	-	-	-	-	-
2	0.830	1	-	-	-	-
3	0.766	0.888	1	-	-	-
4	0.919	0.888	0.889	1	-	-
5	0.835	848	0.884	0.934	1	-
6	0.830	0.838	0.854	0.922	0.934	1

The answers of the research sample indicate complete agreement and agreement, and this was confirmed by the general arithmetic mean for this section, which is (4.2), which is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic average of (3), as well as the standard deviation and general variance

(0.884) (0.449), respectively, which indicates the strength of the sample response The search for the movement of the scale used and the slight dispersion in the answers. Also, this axis enjoys a high degree of internal consistency, and this can be shown through the following table- :

Tables 15: Correlation coefficients for each axis of the first axis – agile services

Paragraph	The first axis	The second axis	The third axis	The fourth axis	The fifth axis
Work site organization axis	1	-	-	-	-
Comprehensive maintenance axis	0.952	1	-	-	-
continuous improvement axis	0.941	0.927	1	-	-
Value stream axis	0.970	0.966	0.970	1	-
Response axis	0.957	0.936	0.926	0.952	1

Section Two: Paragraphs related to the ability of bank administrations to apply the requirements of the Six SICMA

Table 16: Technology

N	Paragraph	Arithmetic Mean	Deviation	Variance
1	Statistical standards and techniques are used to measure the level of performance in the bank's departments	3.62	0.805	0.648
2	The data and information necessary for all services provided in the bank are available.	3.71	0.807	0.651
3	Emphasis is placed on meeting the needs and requirements of customers.	4.33	0.751	0.565
4	The bank is not equipped with modern devices and technologies necessary to speed up the completion of work.	3.60	0.817	0.668
5	There is support and assistance between the various departments of the bank.	4.03	0.813	0.661
6	It employs trained experts and consultants in the field of banking services	4.2	0.717	0.514
7	The performance of the bank is measured objectively	3.51	1.101	1.3
8	Emphasis is placed on continuous improvement programs for the Bank's activities.	3.22	1.151	1.325
9	Bank employees are trained and qualified in quality techniques and methods.	3.96	0.855	0.731
10	The capabilities of the employees are linked to the success of the application of the	4.21	0.717	0.514

	improvement programs, and in return it bears the errors on the employees of the bank.			
11	Effective means of communication with the bank's customers are not provided to determine their satisfaction with the service provided and their suggestions for development	3.79	0.998	0.724
12	The culture and behavior of the bank's employees are changed and they are included in decision-making	4.08	0.787	0.626
13	Emphasis is placed on quality and it is considered the main pillar of the bank's services.	4.00	0.984	0.969
14	Emphasis is placed on meeting the needs and requirements of customers	4.33	0.751	0.565
	The mean ,standard deviation , and general variance	3.41	0.807	0.651

The paragraphs of applying the requirements of the Six Sigma technology in the bank tended towards agreement in the sense that there is a possibility for the bank's management to apply the requirements of the Six Sigma technology, where the arithmetic mean value of the total requirements represented (3.71) which is greater than the hypothesis of (3), and the value of the standard deviation was (0.807), from which it can be concluded that the answers of the sample were homogeneous. As for the direction of each paragraph, it was as follows:

The first: (Statistical standards and techniques are used to measure the level of performance in the bank's departments) I tended towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.62) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.805) and the variance (0.648)

The second: (the necessary data and information are available for the total services provided in the bank) I tended towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.71) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.807) and the variance (0.851)

The third: (there are not enough financial capabilities in the bank) I headed towards the tunnels with an arithmetic mean of (3.33) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.751) and the variance (0.565)

The fourth: (the bank is not equipped with modern devices and techniques necessary to speed up the completion of the work) I tended towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.60), which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.817) and the variance (0.668)

Fifth: (there is support and assistance between the various departments of the bank) I tended to agree with an arithmetic mean whose value is (4.03), which is greater than the hypothetical mean. The standard deviation was (0.813) and the variance was (0.661)

Sixth: (trained experts and consultants are used in the field of banking services) I moved towards

agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (4.2), which is greater than the hypothetical mean. The standard deviation was (0.717) and the variance was (0.514)

Seventh: (performance in the bank is measured objectively) I tended towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.51) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (1.101) and the variance (1.3)

Eighth: (focusing on continuous improvement programs for the activities of the bank) I tended towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.22) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (1.151) and the variance (1.325)

Ninth: (The bank employees are not trained and qualified with quality techniques and methods) I tended to agree with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.96), which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.855) and the variance (0.731)

Tenth: (The potential of the workers is linked to the success of the application of improvement programs and vice versa, the tolerance of errors) I moved towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (4.21), which is greater than the hypothetical mean. The standard deviation was (0.717) and the variance was (0.514).

Eleventh: (effective means of communication with the bank's customers are not provided to determine their satisfaction with the service provided and their suggestions for its development) I moved towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (3.79) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.998) and the variance (0.724).

Twelfth: (The culture and behavior of the bank's employees are changed and their participation in decision-making). The standard deviation was (0.787) and the variance was (0.626).

Thirteenth: (focusing on quality and considering it the basic pillar of bank services) I moved towards agreement with an arithmetic mean whose value is (4.00), which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.984) and the variance (0.969)

Fourteenth: (focus is on meeting the needs and requirements of customers) I tended to agree with an arithmetic mean whose value is (4.33) which is greater than the hypothetical mean and the standard deviation was (0.751) and the variance (0.565)

First: the conclusions

1. It was found through statistical analysis to find out whether there are differences in the possibility of applying the requirements of the SEX technology in banking departments
2. There is a gap between the quality of service expected by customers and the services expected to be provided by the owners working in the bank
3. The weak performance of employees through their low interest in providing services as a result of dissatisfaction, which was generated by the lack of salaries and the lack of incentives on the one hand, and on the other hand, a weak awareness of responsibility and performance measures, lack of transparency and weakness in the efficient application of operations.
4. The traditional methods of work used in providing services and the weakness of modern technologies used in providing services, which results in the slow process and many errors.
5. The bank's management did not have real knowledge about the contemporary administrative approach represented in quality management, as well as the techniques of this approach, including the Essex SEKMA technique, in order to reach excellence and achieve customer satisfaction and other beneficiary bodies, as the attention was focused on providing the final service to customers.

6. The integrated system helps to achieve significant cost savings, in order to reduce waste and waste that occurs in the provision of banking services and the various stages.
7. The application of the integrated system leads to a quick response to customers' requests and the required level of quality, as speed is not at the expense of quality, but rather goes in a balanced manner.
8. The application of any of the aforementioned systems individually does not lead to achieving the optimal strategic performance for the Bank's performance.

Second: recommendations

9. The selected private banks wish to move towards establishing an integrated system between agile production and Six SEKEMs technologies so that their services provided to their customers can compete with banking services provided in international banks.
10. The senior management adopts the philosophy of eliminating waste in its banks to reach zero waste, which secures the efficient achievement of outputs.
11. The need for senior management to adopt lean production methods in the selected banks in order to enhance their impact on the possibility of distinguished services and other impacts on operational performance in banks.
12. Disseminate the concepts of Lean production strategies and Six Sigma techniques among individuals working in Iraqi private banks at all administrative levels through the establishment of training courses, bulletins and advertisements in order to consolidate and enhance the philosophy of integration between Lean production and hexagonal diffraction techniques.
13. The application of concepts, strategies, and methods for each of the Lean production and Six Sigma techniques in accordance with the paragraphs we have identified will enable private banks to enhance their competitive position in the global markets so that they can excel and be creative in the banking fields, reduce waste, reduce costs and raise the levels of banking service.
14. Private banks can face the dynamic competitive challenges and enhance their competitive position in the markets through the use of the integration between Lean production and hexagonal diffraction techniques
15. Establishing an information system on Lean production and Six Sikma techniques via the computer that secures all the necessary information easily and conveniently, giving preliminary indications about the extent of progress in the application of these strategies and methods, giving financial indications on the results of the investigation and conducting comparative analyzes between different periods and using different strategies and methods.
16. The necessity for Iraqi private and governmental banks to pay attention to all lean production strategies and Six Sigma techniques that were identified in this research, to ensure optimal operational performance and entry and competition in global markets.

References

- 1- Abd, Imad Mowaffaq, "The Possibility of Applying Hexagonal Diffraction in Improving the Quality of Hotel Service" submitted to the Council of the Higher Institute for Accounting and Financial Studies / University of Baghdad, which is part of the requirements for obtaining a certificate of cost and management accounting, which is the highest professional certificate in the field of specialization, the holder of which enjoys all the rights and privileges of a certificate PhD, 2013

- 2- Abdullah, Fawaz, "Lean manufacturing and techniques in the process industry with a focus on steel", dissertation for doctoral, University of Pittsburgh, (2003).
- 3- Al-Hakim, Laith Ali Youssef, 2008, Towards the possibility of applying the 6 SIGMA approach based on knowledge management to achieve competitive superiority. An exploratory study of the opinions of a sample of department heads in the Southern Cement General Company, a master's thesis submitted to the Council of the College of Administration and Economics, University of Kufa.
- 4- Al-Hasnawi, Jamil Shu'bah Theban "Dimensions of Lean Production and its Impact on the Dimensions of Operations Performance" submitted to the Board of the College of Administration and Economics / University of Al-Qadisiyah, and it is part of the requirements for obtaining a master's degree in Business Administration, 2013
- 5- Al-Naimi, Muhammad Abdel-Al and Sweis, Ratib Jalil, (2008), Six Sigma: Achieving Accuracy in Quality Management, Concepts and Applications, Ithraa for Publishing and Distribution, first edition, Amman, Jordan.
- 6- Al-Nuaimi, Muhammad Abdel-Aal, (2007), Six Sigma, a modern approach to facing defects, a research presented to the Al-Zaytoonah Scientific Conference in Jordan.
- 7- Al-Qazzaz, Ismail Ibrahim and Al-Hadithi, Rami Hekmat and Corel, Adel Abdul-Malik (2009), Six Sigma and Other Modern Methods in Total Quality Management, Dar Al Masirah for Publishing, Distribution and Printing, first edition, Amman, Jordan.
- 8- Al-Samman, Thaer Ahmed Saadoun, 2008, Integration between Effective Manufacturing Strategy and Lean Manufacturing Methods and Its Impact on Enhancing Operational Performance, An Applied Study in Selected Group of Industrial Organizations in the City of Mosul, Ph.D. Thesis, College of Administration and Economics, University of Mosul.
- 9- Al-Zahrani, Muhammad bin Saleh Muhammad, 2010, the possibility of applying the Six Sigma method in the Security Force Officers Club in Riyadh, a master's thesis submitted to the College of Graduate Studies, Department of Administrative Sciences, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, Saudi Arabia.
- 10- Apel, Wolfgang & Li, Jia Yong & Walton, Vanessa, "Value stream mapping for lean manufacturing implementation", 2007
- 11- Bateson, J., (1995): "Managing Service, Marketing: Text Reading", 2nd ed., London, The Dryden Press.
- 12- Beckman, L. Sara & Rosenfield, B. Donald, "Operations strategy", 1st Ed, McGraw-hill, New York, 2008.
- 13- Goetsch, David, L. & Davis, Stanely, B. "Quality management for organizational excellence introduction to total quality", education international, 6th Ed, 2010.
- 14- Heizer, Jay & Render, Barry, "Operations management", 10th Ed, Pearson, New Jersey, 2011.
- 15- Ibn Saeed, Khaled Saad Abdel Aziz, (2004), Six Sigma: Applications to Service and Industrial Establishments, National Library, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- 16- Idris, Thabet Abdel Rahman, (2006), Efficiency and Quality of Logistics Services, Basic Concepts and Methods of Measurement and Evaluation, University House, Alexandria, Arab Republic of Egypt

- 17- Ismail, Omar Ali, (2006), Six Sigma technology and its applicability in the General Company for Pharmaceutical Industry and Medical Appliances in Nineveh, unpublished Master's Thesis, College of Administration and Economics, University
- 18- Kaliher , T.L. , (2003), Improve Safety Health and Environmental Protection Through The Introduction of Six Sigma, The Graduate School of the University of Wisconsin-Stout, USA.
- 19- Kragewski, Lee J. & Ritzman, Larry P., (2010), Operations Management Processes and Supply Chains, 2th ed., Prentice-Hall, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, USA.
- 20- Magnire, M. , (1999), Cow Boy Quality - Quality Progress, Prentice Hall International, London, UK.
- 21- Muhammad, Raed Majeed Abd "The possibility of using agile accounting tools to reduce costs" unpublished research submitted to the Council of the Higher Institute for Accounting and Financial Studies, University of Baghdad. PhD Distinctions, 2013
- 22- Obeidat, Suleiman Khaled, "Introduction to Production and Operations Management", second edition, Dar Al-Maysara for Publishing, Distribution and Printing, Amman, 2010.
- 23- Park, Sung H, (2003) Six Sigma for Quality and Productivity Promotion. Published by the Asian Productivity Organization, Japan.
- 24- Pearce, John, A. & Robinson, Richard, B., "Strategic management", 8th Ed, McGraw-hill Irwin, 2003.
- 25- Schroeder, Roger, (2004), "Operation Management Contemporary concepts and cases," 7th ed, Mc Graw-Hall Jersey, U.S.A.
- 26- Shaheen, Nidaa Salih, (2001), Evaluation of the Examination System - A Case Study in the Babel/2 Plastic Batteries Factory, an unpublished Master's thesis in Business Administration submitted to the Board of the College of Administration and Economics, University of Baghdad.
- 27- Slack , Nigel & Chambers , Stuart & Johnston , Robert , 2004 , Operations Management , 4th ed. , Prentice Hill, England.